

Influence of Strategic Management Practices on Performance of Turkana County, Kenya

Christopher Koloman Madaraka Mang`Ong`O^{1*}, Dr. Elizabeth Nambuswa Makokha^{1,2}

¹School Of Business, Department Of Business. Jomo Kenyatta University of Agriculture and Technology, P.O. Box 62000 - 00200, Nairobi Kenya

²College of Human Resource Development, Department of Entrepreneurship, procurement, leadership and management. Jomo Kenyatta University of Agriculture and Technology, P.O. Box 62000 - 00200, Nairobi Kenya

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Abstract: The purpose of the study was to examine the effect of strategic management practices on Performance Turkana County. The study was guided by the following specific objective as to identify the influence of strategic evaluation on Performance Turkana County. The study used the following theories as resource based view, goal setting theory, system theory and results based theory. The study adopted a descriptive research design. The target Population was all county directors from all the 13 departments in Turkana County. Data collection instruments used were structured questionnaire. Both primary and secondary data were used to collect data. The researcher self-dropped and picked the duly filled questionnaires. Piloting was done in the County Government of West Pokot to test the validity and reliability of data collection instrument. Data was organised, coded, edited to bring a meaning. Data was analysed and presented using the statistical package for social science SPSS version 24. Both descriptive and inferential statistics was done. Multiple regression was done to test the significant levels of one variable over the other. Analysis of variance was also done. From the findings strategic evaluation ($\beta = 0.514$) was found to be positively related performance of Turkana County, Kenya. From t-test analysis, the t-value was found to be 2.904 and the p-value 0.000. Statistically, this null hypothesis was rejected because $p < 0.05$. Thus, the study accepted the alternative hypothesis and it concluded that strategic evaluation affects performance of Turkana County, Kenya. The findings are of significant to the researchers, academicians, stakeholders and to the entire economy as a whole.

Keywords: Strategic Management, Strategic Evaluation, Strategic Performance.

1. INTRODUCTION

Will K. (2022) states that strategic management is the management of an organization's resources to achieve its goals and objectives. Strategic management practices involve the art and science of formulating, implementing, and evaluating cross-functional decisions that enable an organization to achieve its objectives (Strickland, 2013). It is the formal process, or set of processes, used to determine the strategies (actions) for the organization. It focuses on many areas, including the integration of management, marketing, finance/accounting, production / operations, research and development and computer information systems (McKiernan, 2006). Strategy as practice perspective looks at strategy as something people do. Strategic practice is based on the common sense idea that we have to relate tactics to strategy and strategic goals. This involves asking what kind of choices organizations must make in order to be effective in the short term and at the same time take on this challenge (McKiernan, 2006).

In the world of competition and turbulent business environment, achieving operational performance in organizations is dependent on multiple factors which may be internal and external (Quinn & Hilmer, 2014). Burak (2013) observe that in the modern competitive business environment, organizations from one sector to another can utilize strategic resources in attaining long term and short term goals. Will K. (2022) states that strategic management is the management of an

organization's resources to achieve its goals and objectives. Strategic management practices involve the art and science of formulating, implementing, and evaluating cross-functional decisions that enable an organization to achieve its objectives (Strickland, 2013). It is the formal process, or set of processes, used to determine the strategies (actions) for the organization. Strategy as practice perspective looks at strategy as something people do.

Strategic practice is based on the common sense idea that we have to relate tactics to strategy and strategic goals. This involves asking what kind of choices organizations must make in order to be effective in the short term and at the same time take on this challenge (McKiernan, 2006). Strategic management practice consists of three basic elements, strategy formulation, implementation, evaluation and control (Wheelen & Hunger, 2008). It is within these three elements that strategic management practices are manifested and is also described as the strategic management process. The concept of organizational performance is core to businesses because the major objective of businesses is to make profits. Iravo et. al., (2013) state that one of the important questions in business has been why some organizations succeed and why others fail and this has influenced a study on the drivers of organizational performance. Awino (2011) asserts that for an organization to be successful it has to record high returns and identify performance drivers from the top to the bottom of the organization. Njihia et. al., (2013) highlight performance measurement as one of the tools which helps firms in monitoring performance, identifying the areas that need attention, enhancing motivation, improving communication and strengthening accountability.

Regionally, firm's performance requires strategic management practices involving the art and science of formulating, implementing, and evaluating cross-functional decisions that enable an organization to achieve its objectives (Strickland, 2013). According to Agrawal (2016), it is the formal process, or set of processes, used to determine the strategies (actions) for the organization. For organisational performance to be of quality, strategic management has to focus on many areas, including; the integration of management, marketing, finance / accounting, production/operations, research and development and computer information systems, hence; Strategy as practice for organisational performance perspective looks at strategy as something people do. Strategic practice is based on the common sense idea that we have to relate tactics to strategy and strategic goals. This involves asking what kind of choices organizations must make in order to be effective in the short term and at the same time take on this challenge. Slabbert, et al (2018) did a study on the role of Strategic Management Practices on Organizational Performance of United Nations Development Programme in Mogadishu, Somalia. The findings revealed that there is a strong relationship between strategic management practices and organisational performance.

Locally, strategic management practice consists of four basic elements, strategic planning, implementation, evaluation and control (Makanga, 2017). It is within these four elements that strategic management practices are manifested and is also described as the strategic management process. Strategic leadership is a component of strategic management practice that involves provision of direction and leadership toward implementation of planned strategy. Strategy formulation is the development of long-range plans for the effective management of environmental opportunities and threats, in light of corporate strengths and weaknesses. It includes defining the corporate mission, specifying achievable objectives, developing strategies and setting policy guidelines. Gure et al., (2018) states that strategic management practices is and will always be the backbone of any organisation. According to Timothy et al., (2021) strategic leaderships challenges are the main concerns in many organisation. Simsek, et al., (2015) states that strategic leaders include chief executive officers, company directors, and top managers, leading middle line managers and the wider organization workforce to deliver shareholder and stakeholder value. Strategic leaders are charged with critical choices to facilitate transfer of information, influence and resources with implications for organization performance (Simsek, Heavey & Fox, 2018).

Strategy implementation is the process through which strategies are put into action throughout the organization by deriving short-term objectives from the long-term objectives and further deriving the functional tactics from the business strategy. This process assists management in identifying the specific immediate actions that must be taken in the key functional areas to implement the business strategy (Pearce and Robinson, 2007). Strategy evaluation and control is the process of comparing the actual performance against the desired performance. Strategy evaluation involves setting control processes to continuously review, evaluate and provide feedback concerning the implemented strategies to determine if the desired results are being accomplished such that corrective measures may be taken if warranted (Sasaka, 2017).

Strategic leadership is the leader's ability to anticipate, envision, and maintain flexibility and to empower others to create strategic change as necessary (Hitt, Ireland, & Hoskisson 2007). Mungania and Karanja (2015) established that leadership is a major factor affecting the implementation of strategic plans. Understanding the effects of leadership on organizational performance requires examining multiple levels of leadership simultaneously. In organizations of any size, it is likely that organizational performance should be related to the aggregate effects of leaders at different hierarchical levels. Regardless

of the effects of an individual leader, alignment or misalignment of leaders across hierarchical levels may enhance or detract from the successful implementation of a strategic initiative. Strategic thinking makes managers to be in tune with what is required to galvanize the whole processes in the firm for better achievement going forward. It is a process through which businesses learn how to define perspective by applying teamwork, critical thinking and continuous improvement (Kiaei, Hatam, Moraveji, Moradi, Ahmadzadeh & Ghanavati, 2016). It is a process that embeds the manner in which people think and rethink, evaluate, view, and conduct the future for themselves and others (Al-Qatamin & Esam, 2018). It contributes to broad, general, overarching concepts that focus the future direction of an organization based on anticipated environmental conditions (Goldman, 2016).

Nzuve and Nyaega (2012) opined that Performance management and improvement is at the heart of strategic management because a lot of strategic thinking is geared towards defining and measuring performance. Awino (2011) asserts that for an organization to be successful it has to record high returns and identify performance drivers from the top to the bottom of the organization. Organizations create transformational leadership teams who have the knowledge, insight and experience to help organizations create a flexible, scalable and cost effective platform for delivering functional and business enabling processes. Tamrakar (2010) indicate that improvement in Organisational performance is also informed by the need to grow and expand services, take advantage of opportunities or merely to implement new knowledge which can come up with action plans. In many developing countries, the issue of firms performance is a challenge that needs to be addressed given the low quality of service provision and the pressing needs of the poor (Besley and Ghatak, 2007). Khalid (2010) supports this view when he states that local councils in Malaysia continue to face pressure to improve their firms. The increased level of education of the population has led to a more vocal and more discerning citizenry that expects better services and accountability from its local government. Moreover, rapid industrialization and urbanization of countries have created a challenging environment for the local government (Khalid, 2010).

Tamrakar (2010) affirms that in Nepal, public organisational performance has remained lower than what was targeted when Nepal announced delivery of public services to its people through a planned development effort. The USA is well known for its significant improvements in ensuring strategic management practices in its devolved units which has seen an explosion in development of infrastructure for economic sustainability. The rural communities in the USA have grown to enviable levels and most of the devolved units are deemed semi or partially autonomous (Kelegama, 2011). Ever since the introduction of counties in Latin America development planners and academic scholars have underlined the role co-operatives should and do play in stepping-up development. This official and popular support for devolution strengthening has been omnipresent and has received a prominent place in such diverse economic political approaches have been witnessed.

Regionally, the problem of Organisational performance due to poor strategic management practices or culture is a problem that is faced by many towns in the world, especially in Africa and other developing countries. Humphreys (1998) alluded to the fact that, delivery of services has a direct and immediate effect on the quality of the lives of the people in a given community. Poor services can make it difficult to attract business or industry to an area and it will also limit job opportunities for residents (Humphreys, 1998). Hence, as Besley and Ghatak (2007) indicate, improving public organisational performance is one of the biggest challenges worldwide. Gwayi (2010) argues that mu Nzuve and Nyaega (2012) opined that Performance management and improvement is at the heart of strategic management because a lot of strategic thinking is geared towards defining and measuring performance. Awino (2011) asserts that for an organization to be successful it has to record high returns and identify performance drivers from the top to the bottom of the organization. Municipalities in South Africa face serious challenges in implementing Organisational performance options that will enhance existing structures in the sphere of local government points towards the need for strategies to improve Organisational performance. To date, there are limited studies that have formally investigated the causes of poor Organisational performance and the strategies that can be implemented to improve the Organisational performance in local authorities. The Rwandese Association of Local Government Authorities (RALGA) in 2010 reported on the factors affecting Organisational performance in local governments.

Turkana County is one of the 47 counties in the Republic of Kenya. Turkana North District is situated in the northern half of the Rift Valley Province. It is one of the 43 districts of the Rift Valley Province. The district is administratively divided into seven divisions, 26 locations and 72 sub-locations. The district is administered under Turkana county council. Settlement pattern in the district is determined by the availability of pastures and social facilities mainly found in urban centres. Turkana people under normal circumstances settle in the plains. However due to variations in weather, very few of

them settle permanently in one place. Kakuma division has the largest number of people due to the presence of refugees' camp in the town that has led to the concentration of many NGOs that are providing employment to the local people. In addition, the division has good climate, fertile soils and frequent rains making farming a viable venture.

“The Vision of the county government of Turkana is of choice to Invest, Work and Live in”. While the mission is to provide affordable, accessible and sustainable quality service, enhancing community participation and creating a secure climate for political, social and economic development through the commitment of a motivated and dedicated team. The county government is embracing a set of strategies to optimize its organisational performance (CADP, 2016). In terms of Revenue enhancement, the county government is embracing the strategies of automation of revenue collection processes both at the headquarters and field offices, sealing revenue leakages, increasing public awareness on importance of fee and user charges payment and reduction of default rates through strengthening of enforcement and compliance mechanism. The role of the County Government as the catalyst of economic development as well as political and social stability is undoubtedly critical given its status as the government at the second level at grassroots level (County Governments Act, 2012). With certain autonomy power, the County is measured to enhance the increased demand from the communities for a more customer oriented and higher standard of both rural and urban services. The County Government of Turkana, has the following thirteen (13) departments/ministries: office of the governor, human resource department, county public service board, Finance and Economic Planning, Lands, Housing and Physical Planning, Trade, Industry, Cooperative Development and Tourism, Agriculture, Livestock and Fisheries, Public Service Management, Public, Works, Roads and Transport, Water, Energy, Forestry and Natural Resources, Information, Communication and E-Government, Education, Youth Affairs, Culture and Social Services and Health Services. For effective County government performance aforementioned mandates, there creates need to employ strategic management practices to ensure utmost value for the public (County Government of Turkana Website, 2017).

The world is increasingly getting complex, and so are organizations. With multiple dynamic and competing factors coming into play, there is need to put in place effective strategic management plan to meet modern management challenges. To compete successfully in this environment, organizations continually need to improve their performance by reducing cost, innovating products and processes and improving quality, productivity and speed to market (Rumelt, 2011). Proper strategic management practices should provide a platform for all relevant stakeholders in project identification, timely and adequate absorption of development funds to implementation of planned projects and programs.

A number of studies on strategic management practices in various organizations have been carried out in the past. On the international front Kandie (2010) who studied on influence of strategic management practices in governments in Europe using a correlational research design noted that change is needed when environmental conditions change. In Africa the Rwandese Association of Local Government Authorities (RALGA) in 2010 reported on the factors affecting Performance in local governments. However, it did not empirically examine the strategies that can be adopted to improve Performance in local authorities. Locally a study by Njau (2001) on challenges of strategy implementation concluded that whereas some firms realized the need to change their strategy due to change in the competitive environment, they lacked finances and managerial empowerment to do so. This study therefore seeks to identify the influence of strategic evaluation practice on Performance of Turkana County

2. STRATEGIC EVALUATION ON PERFORMANCE OF TURKANA COUNTY

Organizations, regardless of size, strive to remain competitive on a constant basis in order to stay in business and prosper (Al Saadi, & Al Mahasina, 2021). However, owing to the dynamic and tumultuous business climate, a competitive organization may fall well short of its aims, goals, and objectives. Adani et al., (2021) avers that all business entities encounter dynamic and sometimes complex situations occasioned by huge discontinuities that take place in a typical business environment. In such a constantly changing environment, organizations require a strategic look at issues. Capturing this, Al-Qatamin and Esam (2018) opine that the changes in the market call for an innovative thinking technique to be able to successfully navigate through the market hurdles. This brings to the fore the concept of strategic evaluation. The study by Abdalla (2015), argues that more than ever organizations need to achieve the very best training and performance improvement possible. Today's competitive environment requires a workforce that cannot only learn quickly, but that can rapidly and consistently transform new learning into enhanced individual, team, and organizational performance. The source finds that thoughtful, efficient, and constructive evaluation is at the heart of continuous improvement and is vital to unlocking the desperately needed potential of learning for performance improvement.

Similar sentiments are shared in Chepkwony (2016) where it is argued that when the evaluation is held as sacred in an organization. The two studies agree on the fact that there is always the feeling that an individual needs to perform when there is a prospective evaluation than when there is none. For this reason, it is believed in both cases that strategy evaluation impacts performance as it drives up the urge to perform highly and impress during evaluation. However, the effect of evaluation can be separated into two aspects of formative and summative assessment. Its findings suggested that strategic summative evaluations provide a method for verifying the efficiency and effectiveness of organizational strategies, as well as a way to determine whether the strategy being implemented is moving the business toward its intended strategic objectives.

The evaluations were also found to help in establishing when and what actions are necessary to align business performance with the targets. In Yuliansyah, Rammal, and Rose (2016), summative evaluations are lauded for their comprehensiveness in establishing performance. The argument presented therein is that it is rather impossible for an evaluation to thoroughly measure performance accurately unless the period has come to an end. While this may be true to some extent, other studies have also opined that there are periodical criteria that are used and do not require for the end of a financial period for them to be valid. Chenhall (2005) opines that strategic evaluations begin by establishing a performance target according to business objectives. This performance target includes both qualitative and quantitative performance benchmarks to which the individual and organizational performance is compared to actual. Qualitative benchmarks are subjective factors such as skills, competencies, and flexibility. Quantitative benchmarks include "hard facts" such as net profit, earnings per share of stock or staff turnover rates.

In the study by Goodwin and Wright (2001), strategic evaluations are observed to work under the assumption that because the business environment is dynamic, variances will commonly exist between ideal and actual performance. Regular strategic evaluations provide an objective, effective way for a business to evaluate, analyse and modify performance expectations. A favourable variance can tell a business what it's doing right and confirm it's on the right track while a negative variance can be a signal that the performance of management and staff needs to change. With such information, Bunnefeld, Hoshino, and Milner-Gulland (2011) advise that business is well positioned to work towards the improvement of performance to match or surpass expectations.

Additionally, the source suggests that summative evaluations ought to be about measuring performance concerning the standards set at the beginning of a period. To make evaluations effective in influencing future performance, it is vital for management to consider revising goals at the end of a season if there is a need to do so. The purpose is to make goals both challenging and realistic (Tayler, 2010). Baker, Collier and Jayaraman (2017) argue that when summative strategic evaluations pinpoint areas where the business did meeting strategic objectives, corrective actions can attempt to solve the problem in future periods. A good example cited in the source is if a business establishes strategic technical goals are not achieved because staff do not have up-to-date qualifications, the business can design training programs that bring skill sets in line with technical objectives.

Pérez-López, Moreno-Romero and Barkemeyer (2015) argue that if a business discovers the business object itself is out of line – such as unrealistic goals – it can take steps to change the objective and bring it to the line with real-life potential. Summative evaluation role in organizational performance was the subject of investigation in Alidrisi and Mohamed (2012) where it was established that it creates the feeling of responsibility among management and staff of a firm. Previous strategy evaluations also provide guidance and directions that are to be followed in subsequent periods for better performance. Summative evaluations in business are also said to be beneficial in positively influencing performance because they seek to reveal the deficiencies that have caused an aspect to fail. This kind of evaluation is both forward-looking and also considering historical information. According to Bhattacharyya and Cummings (2015), its purpose is always to look for better ways of achieving organizational goals. It does not matter whether goals have been achieved or not; summative evaluations must still present recommendations for better practices in the future nevertheless.

With successful strategic management practices means that the organisations will be able to achieve its objectives in a timely and in competitiveness since it is concerned with the overall productivity in an organization in terms of stock turnover, customers, profitability and market share. The concept of organizational performance is core to businesses because the major objective of businesses is to make profits. Iravo et. al., (2013) state that one of the important questions in business has been why some organizations succeed and why others fail and this has influenced a study on the drivers of organizational performance. Organizational performance is concerned with the overall productivity in an organization in terms of stock

turnover, customers, profitability and market share. The concept of organizational performance is core to businesses because the major objective of businesses is to make profits. Iravo et. al., (2013) state that one of the important questions in business has been why some organizations succeed and why others fail and this has influenced a study on the drivers of organizational performance.

Fwaya (2006) views performance as a formula for the assessment of the functioning of an organization under certain parameters such as productivity, employee' morale and effectiveness. Nzuve and Nyaega (2012) opined that Performance management and improvement is at the heart of strategic management because a lot of strategic thinking is geared towards defining and measuring performance. Awino (2011) asserts that for an organization to be successful it has to record high returns and identify performance drivers from the top to the bottom of the organization. Odhiambo (2009) identified three approaches to performance in an organization which are the goal approach, which states that an organization pursues definite identifiable goals. This approach describes performance in terms of the attainment of these goals. The second approach is the systems resource approach which defines performance as a relationship between an organization and its environment. This concept defines performance according to an organization's ability to secure the limited and valued resources in the environment. The third approach is the process perspective which defines performance in terms of the behaviour of the human resource of an organization (Waiganjo et. al., 2012). Kiragu (2005) highlights performance in terms of four perspectives which are the financial, customer, internal processes and innovativeness. The financial perspective identifies the key financial drivers of enhancing performance which are profit margin, asset turnover, leverage, cash flow, and working capital (Odhuno and Wadongo, 2010).

Odhiambo (2009) states that the first approach describes performance in terms of the attainment of these goals. The second approach is the systems resource approach which defines performance as a relationship between an organization and its environment. This concept defines performance according to an organization's ability to secure the limited and valued resources in the environment. The third approach is the process perspective which defines performance in terms of the behaviour of the human resource of an organization (Waiganjo et. al., 2012).

Kiragu (2005) highlights performance in terms of four perspectives which are the financial, customer, internal processes and innovativeness. The financial perspective identifies the key financial drivers of enhancing performance which are profit margin, asset turnover, leverage, cash flow, and working capital (Odhuno and Wadongo, 2010). The customer focus describes performance in terms of brand image, customer satisfaction, and customer retention and customer profitability. Internal processes involve the efficiency of all the systems in the organization while innovativeness is concerned with the ease with which a firm is able to adapt to changing conditions.

3. METHOD

This study adopted a descriptive research design with the target population of 45 middle level managers in the county government of Turkana. Since the study population was small, the study worked with the entire population which is census. Data collection instrument used was a structured questionnaire was administered to the respondents. Piloting was done to test the validity and reliability of the research instrument. The data was reduced, organized, coded, edited, classified using a table and analysed to bring out the meaning under each of the factors. Once data was collected, it was crosschecked and verified for errors, completeness and consistency. It was then coded, entered and analysed descriptively using IBM Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SSPS 23). Pearson correlation analysis was used to test the relationship between variables in the study hypotheses. ANOVA multiple linear regression analysis was adopted and computed to determine the statistical relationship between the independent variable and the dependent.

4. DISCUSSION

In the study by Goodwin and Wright (2001), strategic evaluations are observed to work under the assumption that because the business environment is dynamic, variances will commonly exist between ideal and actual performance. Regular strategic evaluations provide an objective, effective way for a business to evaluate, analyse and modify performance expectations. A favourable variance can tell a business what it's doing right and confirm it's on the right track while a negative variance can be a signal that the performance of management and staff needs to change. The study sought to identify the influence of strategic evaluation practice on Performance of Turkana County. The findings are presented in a five point Likerts scale where SA=strongly agree, A=agree, N=neutral, D=disagree, SD=strongly disagree and T=total.

From table 4.1 below, the respondents were asked whether organizational strategic evaluation includes the shared beliefs, norms and values within the business. The distribution of findings showed that 53.0 percent of the respondents strongly agreed, 30.0 percent of them agreed, 10.0 percent of the respondents were neutral while 7.0 percent disagreed. None of the respondents strongly disagreed to the statement. These findings implied that majority of the respondents agreed that organizational strategic evaluation includes the shared beliefs, norms and values within the business.

The respondents were also asked whether for a strategy within an organization to develop and be implemented successfully, it must fully align with the county's policies. The distribution of the responses indicated that 51.0 percent strongly agreed to the statement, 34.0 percent of them agreed and 10.0 percent of them were neutral while 5.0 percent of them disagreed. None of the respondents strongly disagreed to the statement. These findings implied that majority of the respondents agreed that for a strategy within an organization to develop and be implemented successfully, it must fully align with the county's policies.

The respondents were also asked whether periodic monitoring and evaluation must be established within an organization to support and establish an organizational culture that embraces the organization's strategy over time. The distribution of the responses indicated that 42.0 percent strongly agreed to the statement, 43.0 percent of them agreed, 8.0 percent of them were neutral while 7.0 percent of them disagreed and strongly disagreed to the statement respectively. These findings implied that majority of the respondents agreed that periodic monitoring and evaluation must be established within an organization to support and establish an organizational culture that embraces the organization's strategy over time.

Further, the respondents were further asked whether to make evaluations effective in influencing future performance, it is vital for management to consider revising goals at the end of a season if there is a need to do so. The distribution of the responses indicated that 50.0 percent strongly agreed to the statement, 39.0 percent of them agreed while 11.0 percent of them were neutral. None of the respondents disagreed or strongly disagreed to the statement. These findings implied that majority of the respondents agreed that to make evaluations effective in influencing future performance, it is vital for management to consider revising goals at the end of a season if there is a need to do so.

Finally, the respondents were further asked whether frequent evaluations requires managers to think beyond routine procedures in order to concentrate on intended long-term strategic business purposes. The distribution of the responses indicated that 52.0 percent strongly agreed to the statement, 33.0 percent of them agreed while 15.0 percent of them were neutral. None of the respondents disagreed or strongly disagreed to the statement. These findings implied that majority of the respondents agreed that frequent evaluations requires managers to think beyond routine procedures in order to concentrate on intended long-term strategic business purposes.

Table 4.1: Influence of Strategic Evaluation Practice on Performance of Turkana County

Statements on Strategic Evaluation	SA	A	N	D	SD
Organizational strategic evaluation includes the shared beliefs, norms and values within the business.	% 53.0	30.0	10.0	7.0	0
For a strategy within an organization to develop and be implemented successfully, it must fully align with the county's policies.	% 51.0	34.0	10.0	5.0	0
Periodic monitoring and evaluation must be established within an organization to support and establish an organizational culture that embraces the organization's strategy over time	% 42.0	43.0	8.0	4.0	3.0
To make evaluations effective in influencing future performance, it is vital for management to consider revising goals at the end of a season if there is a need to do so	% 50.0	39.0	11.0	0	0
Frequent evaluations requires managers to think beyond routine procedures in order to concentrate on intended long-term strategic business purposes	% 52.0	33.0	15.0	0	0

4.2 Inferential Statistics

4.2.1 Pearson Correlation

The study sought to establish the strength of the relationship between independent and dependent variables of the study. Pearson correlation coefficient was computed at 95 percent confidence interval (error margin of 0.05). Table 4.2 illustrates the findings of the study.

Table 4.2: Correlation Matrix

		Performance of Turkana County
Strategic evaluation	Pearson Correlation	.575**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000
	N	43

As shown on Table 4.2 above, the p-value for strategic evaluation was found to be 0.000 which is less than the significant level of 0.05, ($p < 0.05$). The result indicated that Pearson Correlation coefficient (r-value) of 0.575, which represented an average, positive relationship between strategic evaluations on performance of Turkana County, Kenya.

4.2.2 Multiple Linear Regression

Multiple linear regressions were computed at 95 percent confidence interval (0.05 margin error) to show the multiple linear relationships between the independent and dependent variables of the study.

4.2.2.1 Coefficient of Determination (R^2)

Table 4.3 below shows that the coefficient of correlation (R) is positive 0.563. This means that there is a positive correlation between strategic management practices on performance of Turkana County, Kenya. The coefficient of determination (R Square) indicates that 27.6% of performance of Turkana County, Kenya is influenced by the strategic planning. The adjusted R^2 however, indicates that 25.3% of performance of Turkana County, Kenya, Kenya is influenced by the strategic management practices leaving 74.7% to be influenced by other factors that were not captured in this study.

Table 4.3: Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.563 ^a	.276	.253	9.20118

a. Predictors: (Constant), Strategic Evaluation,

4.2.2.2 Analysis of Variance

Table 4.4 shows the Analysis of Variance (ANOVA). The p-value is 0.000 which is < 0.05 indicates that the model is statistically significant in predicting how strategic management practices influences performance of Turkana County, Kenya. The results also indicate that the independent variables are predictors of the dependent variable with an F test of 53.162.

Table 4.4: ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	622.032	1	253.314	53.162	.000 ^b
	Residual	1274.232	42	12.961		
	Total	1896.000	43			

4.2.2.3 Regression Coefficients

From the Coefficients (Table 4.5) the regression model can be derived as follows:

$$Y = 52.063 + 0.514X_1$$

The results in table 4.5 indicate that all the independent variables have a significant positive effect on performance of Turkana County, Kenya. The influential variable is strategic evaluation had a coefficient of 0.514 (p-value =0.000). According to this model when all the independent variables values are zero, performance of Turkana County, Kenya will have a score of 52.063.

Table 4.5: Regression Coefficients

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	52.063	2.828		60.212	.000
Strategic evaluation	.514	.170	.376	2.904	.000

4.2.3 Hypotheses Testing

4.2.3.1 Hypothesis One

Ho₁: Strategic evaluation does not have a significant effect on performance of Turkana County, Kenya.

From Table 4.5 above, strategic evaluation ($\beta = 0.514$) was found to be positively related performance of Turkana County, Kenya. From t-test analysis, the t -value was found to be 2.904 and the ρ -value 0.000. Statistically, this null hypothesis was rejected because $\rho < 0.05$. Thus, the study accepted the alternative hypothesis and it concluded that strategic evaluation affects performance of Turkana County, Kenya.

5. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

The study sought to identify the influence of strategic evaluation practice on Performance of Turkana County. The findings revealed that organizational strategic evaluation includes the shared beliefs, norms and values within the business and that for a strategy within an organization to develop and be implemented successfully, it must fully align with the county's policies. These findings implied that periodic monitoring and evaluation must be established within an organization to support and establish an organizational culture that embraces the organization's strategy over time. Further the findings indicated that to make evaluations effective in influencing future performance, it is vital for management to consider revising goals at the end of a season if there is a need to do so and that frequent evaluations requires managers to think beyond routine procedures in order to concentrate on intended long-term strategic business purposes.

In conclusion basing on the findings, strategic evaluation ($\beta = 0.514$) was found to be positively related performance of Turkana County, Kenya. From t-test analysis, the t -value was found to be 2.904 and the ρ -value 0.000. Statistically, this null hypothesis was rejected because $\rho < 0.05$. Thus, the study accepted the alternative hypothesis and it concluded that strategic evaluation affects performance of Turkana County, Kenya.

The study came up with a number of recommendations. The study recommends that the management should ensure the alignment of organisations shared beliefs, norms and values within the business with the county's policies a strategy in order to be successful. Management to consider revising goals at the end of a season if there is a need while supporting and establish an organizational culture that embraces the organization's strategy over time. There should be frequent evaluations to enable managers to think beyond routine procedures in order to concentrate on intended long-term strategic business purposes. Management framework adopted should oversee the various activities of institutions project or other activities of an organization.

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